

COURT'S ROLE IN ARBITRATION: ENSURING FAIRNESS WITHOUT OVERREACH

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Abstract: Arbitration is the submission of a dispute between two or more Arbitration, parties for decision by a third party of their choice, so says John Paris. This Dispute, Parties, definition is akin to Ronald Bernstein's idea of arbitration to wit "an agreement Third party, of parties that a dispute between them be settled by a tribunal of their choice. Tribunal, Agreement, Russell defines arbitration as a written agreement to submit present or four Arbitrator, differences to arbitration whether an arbitrator is named or not. Another Written reference work has defined arbitration as the reference of a dispute or difference agreement between not less than two parties for determination, after hearing both sides in a judicial manner, by a person or persons other than a court of competent jurisdiction. In the same vein, Justice Maxwell's view is that "arbitration is a process whereby a private disinterested person called an arbitrator, chosen by the parties to a dispute ...acting in a judicial fashion but without regard to technicalities applying either existing law or norms agreed by the parties, and acting in accordance with equity, good conscience and perceived merit of the dispute makes an award to resolve the dispute.

Keywords: Arbitration, Dispute Resolution, Arbitral Award, Arbitration Agreement, Tribunal

Introduction

The foray of scholarly expositions above can easily be collapsed into one dimension namely, arbitration is a system of judicial resolution of a civil dispute, private in nature, relying on national laws and or international instruments with little must be stressed that arbitration settles issues between parties. This is important because there are other methods of resolving issues such as valuation, mediation, conciliation and similar forms which necessarily do not amount to arbitration. The acid test for determining whether an exercise is arbitration or not is firstly, the existence of a hearing in a judicial manner. Only where the parties are heard in this manner, does the exercise qualify as arbitration. Secondly, arbitral award becomes binding immediately it is made by the arbitrator whereas in other forms of ADR, the consent and acceptance of the term by the parties are necessary for the terms to be binding. It is important to mention that not all arbitration agreements are required to be in writing. Written arbitration agreement is the requirement of arbitration agreement under the Act as customary and common law arbitration agreements are not required to be in writing.

Court:

According to Black's Law Dictionary, a court is, inter alia, a governmental body consisting of one or more judges who sit to adjudicate disputes and administer justice. The same source also adopts the definition of court proffered by W. J. Hughes who wrote that: A court... is a permanently organized body, with independent judicial defined by law, meeting at a time and place fixed by law for the judicial public administration of justice. Amongst the meanings assigned to the word court, in Webster's New Collegiate Dictionary is an official assembly for the transaction of judicial business, a judge or judges in session. It does not require a genius to figure out that both the court and an arbitral panel perform the same function, the former in public setting and the latter in private setting. Since both a court of law and an arbitral panel decide matters in a judicial manner, what place has the court in arbitral proceedings?

The Role of Court in Arbitration

To comprehend fully the question of courts' roles in arbitration, we call to mind that an arbitral panel is set up by the parties. Consequently such a body does not possess the coercive powers of the state and therefore is seriously handicapped in certain respects. Courts provide essential services to the arbitral process in Nigeria and it is absolutely difficult for arbitration to exist without the courts. We have mild and pure theory of the autonomy of arbitration practice and proceeding. Some are of the opinion that arbitration is subject to the court and in fact, that arbitration cannot decide with binding force hence some judges are antagonistic of arbitration and as such interfere unnecessarily in arbitration matters. Some experts in arbitration feel that the courts should be excluded in all arbitration matters. Both sides have their reasons but suffice it to state that such reasons should be weighed on the practical logic of what arbitration is. Arbitration cannot be an institution floating on none legal firmament and not subject to any control at all. Arbitration and courts should exist as partners and not a state of antagonism. Outstandingly the arbitral processes would need state assistance where difficulties arise in the following circumstances: (i) Enforcement of arbitration agreement

- (ii) Appointment of arbitrators
- (iii) Control of arbitral procedures
- (iv) Determination of arbitrability of subject matter of arbitration
- (v) Interim measures of protection
- (vi) Enforcement of awards
- (vii) Impeachment of awards
- (viii) Impeachment of arbitrator
- (ix) Stay of proceedings
- (x) Impeachment and setting aside of arbitration agreement
- (xi) Summoning of a witness held under the public law in prison

(i) Enforcement of Arbitration Agreement

Even when parties had, ab initio, in good faith entered into an agreement to settle their dispute by means of arbitration, it may and have sometimes been the case that one of the parties may renege from the agreement and sue in a court of law. This of course, defeats the entire purpose of arbitration. In such a situation, there is not much the aggrieved party can do by himself alone. The law is that under the circumstances, the innocent party shall seek the assistance of the court. To succeed in invoking the assistance of the court, there must be evidence of an agreement to arbitrate and this can be proved by providing. (a) A document signed by the parties (b) Exchange of letters, telex, telegrams of other means of communication which provide a record of the arbitration agreement.

(c) An exchange of points of claim and or defense in which the existence of an arbitration agreement is averred by one party and not denied by the other. Furthermore, a contractual document incorporating an arbitration clause referable to the contract suffices as a proof of the arbitration agreement. Section 4 of the arbitration and Conciliation Act provides that where an action which is a subject matter of arbitration is brought before a court, a party therein may request the court of stay proceedings and refer the parties to arbitration, provided that the request for stay is not made later than when the applicant submits his first statement on the substance of the dispute. Section 5 of the same Act makes similar provision. There is no doubt that these are desirable provisions in the interest of arbitration. However, these sections of the law need to be finetuned. Section 4 (2) empowers the court to retain the matter in its list as *lis pendis* while arbitration is commenced and continued which may result in rendering an award. This sub section makes it possible for the court to still have some jurisdiction over the subject matter of the dispute while arbitration is in progress. This is Pilate washing his hand while in his palace, Christ's trial rages on. This should not be. The law should be that the courts should completely hands off and strike out the matter, because at that stage no cause of action has arisen. The arbitral panel will then be free to commence and settle the dispute on a clean and fresh slate. These sections of the law have drawn much criticism from Scholars because of the inelegance of draftsmanship. However, S.5 saved the day by granting the court the discretion either to grant stay or refuse same in deserving situations. This is because S.4 is unacceptable in law as it denied the court the right to exercise any discretion as it provides that the court shall grant stay in all situations wherein the applicants apply before taking any step in the proceedings and it further states in S.4 (2) that notwithstanding that the court has refused stay, arbitration may nonetheless commence and continue. This seems a challenge on the jurisdiction of the court which is not the philosophy or arbitration. Arbitration is not an attack on the institution known as the court, rather they are both partners in dispensing justice (one within the public domain whereas the other in the private). However, where parties have agreed to have their matter taken by arbitration, the court should assist the parties by ensuring that the term of their agreement is respected the court should assist the defaulting party to escape the effect of the agreement he entered into with the other party. This is because there is every reason to resume that reasonable parties will wish to have their relationships created by their contract and claims arising therefrom, irrespective of whether the contract is effective, decided by the same Tribunal and not by the court. While granting or refusing the application for stay by the court, it is necessary to always bear in mind the powerful commercial reasoning for upholding arbitration clauses

unless it is clear that this would offend the policy of the illegality rule. Courts should therefore be slow to find reasons to assume jurisdiction over a matter that the parties have agreed to refer to arbitration. It must also be remembered that the whole thrust of arbitration whether domestic or international was geared towards minimizing court involvement in matters which the parties have agreed to submit to arbitration. Current unnecessary court interventions in arbitration proceedings are to be avoided unless it is for the purpose of lending crucial assistance to the arbitral process. This is because unnecessary and unreasonable court intervention may tend to encourage parties to stall arbitration proceedings. In short, the role of the court should be to support and not to displace arbitral process.

(ii) Appointment of Arbitrators

Parties may find themselves unable to agree with regard to constituting the arbitral panel. Here again, the arbitral process is stalled and unless a coercive action is taken, the objective is defeated. It is, therefore, desirable that a willing party who obviously needs assistance shall receive the same from the court. Section 7 and Article 6 of Act make elaborate provisions for constituting an arbitral panel in the absence of parties providing for this. Interestingly, S.7 (3) (i) thereof provides that any party may request the court to take the necessary measure, where an appointing authority, a third party including an institution fails to perform the duty of constituting an arbitral panel. This section is elucidated further in Article 6 which contains provision for seeking court assistance in appointing a sole arbitrator. Section 7 of the Act has created some difficulties

with regard to the extent of court intervention on the issue. Three Divisions of the Nigerian Court of Appeal in various decisions have sent legal practitioners on a wild goose chase with regard to the certainty of curial solution to the correct interpretation of section 7 (4) of the Act which stipulates that a decision of court arrived at on the issue of appointment of arbitrators is final and not appealable. Text-writers are not unanimous in their interpretation of the section. Nevertheless one thing is certain, any one informed of the contemporary scene in Nigeria would opt for a process that would not lead to elongation a delay in the arbitral process such as would be the case if appeals were allowed up to the Supreme Court level before arbitration can commence. It staggers the imagination to contemplate the colossal loss or even destruction of some types of the res if the ultimate appeal is allowed given the time by which a simple matter goes up to the Supreme Court. It must however, be stated that the right of appeal must not be crucified on the altar of speed as right of appeal is a constitutional right granted by the Constitution to ever aggrieved party. It is then unconstitutional for S.7 (4) to have barred the right of appeal in deserving situations.

(iii) Control of Arbitral Proceedings Once parties submit to arbitration, they are bound to attend the proceedings and produce documents and witnesses to the arbitral panel. Except the parties agree, otherwise, the arbitral panel has power to decide the mode of arbitration. The choice is selected from

(a) Holding an oral hearing, for the presentation of parties' evidence or oral arguments.

(b) Deciding on the basis of documents or other materials

(c) A combination of oral hearing and documentary or materials i.e. use of both (a) and (b) above.

Where option (a) or (c) is in place, parties are required to submit themselves for cross- and of course to comply with the directions of the arbitrator. If a party defaults any of these, the arbitral tribunal makes

whatever decision it deems appropriate. However, where there is need for a third party involvement in the proceedings neither a party to the arbitration, nor the arbitral panel can compel such a third party participation or action in the arbitral process. Therefore, this calls for state aid. Here again the court has a role to play for the continuation or success of arbitral proceedings. The Act laid foundation for this court intervention by providing that "any party to an arbitral proceedings may, issue out a writ of subpoena ad testificandum or subpoena duces tecum. However, the issuing of these orders can only be done by courts since no person has the power to coerce another. Taking care of this, the law also provides for a court to order attendance of a witness to court to testify for or furnish documents to the arbitral tribunal. Such order is so sweeping that even the prison authorities are bound to produce a prisoner for such purpose to the arbitral tribunal.

(iv) Determination of Arbitrability

Arbitrability deals with the issue of whether a subject matter of arbitration is one which the law recognizes as capable, of being resolved in private arena. This also has to do with the scope and extent of the arbitration agreement and its validity. Generally, an arbitrable dispute is one that is capable of being resolved by compromise through accord and satisfaction. ¹⁵ In general parties do not have the capacity to decide whether the subject matter of their dispute is arbitrable or not, that is the province of the jurisprudence of the state. Thus parties are bound by the state's imposed limit in this regard. Certain cases are quite plain and do not need any brain racking. Disputes bordering on criminal offence are clearly outside the range of arbitration. The same goes with illegal contracts." Void acts do not give rise to any right, hence they are not arbitrable. Jurisdiction is at the heart of arbitrability. Jurisdiction here refers to the power of an arbitral tribunal to decide a dispute presented before it. But this is subtle. The matter can be approached from two perspectives. At the first level, the question is whether within the confines of the law governing the contract as established, the issue under consideration is covered by the arbitral agreement. At the 'second level, the issue is within the purview of the general law, whether the subject matter of the dispute is one capable of resolution by arbitration. In the first case, the law is clear that it is the arbitral tribunal that decides on this. However, it has also been opined that in view of the phrase "existence or validity of an arbitration agreement" in section 12 (1), the arbitral tribunal has power to also handle the second level approach. This seems plausible, as generally a court of law has power to decide on its jurisdiction, but it may not be advantageous in this instance. We are of the view that such issue of primordial jurisdiction should be handled by the court or the arbitral tribunal depending on the stage at which the issue is raised. If the matter is raised before the arbitral tribunal, the tribunal shall have jurisdiction to deal with the matter. On the other hand if a party in disobedience to the arbitration agreement had taken the matter to court in the believe that the tribunal has no jurisdiction to deal with the matter, the court should be allowed to deal with the matter because the issue is radical and a final curial decision will abort arbitrators going into an exercise that would amount to a wild goose chase. If the arbitral panel decides on that question and of course, proceeds to go through the whole hog of arbitral proceedings arriving at an award which upon challenge is set aside on grounds of absence of primordial jurisdiction, neither the party nor the arbitral tribunal is benefited.¹⁶ Indeeds this reasoning seems to inform the ratio of *Bendel Feeds & Flour Mills Ltd vSeaboard Sale Corporation & Shipping Company Ltd*. wherein the Court of Appeal held that: It seems

right... in principle that if a party contended that is not a party to a contract in which an arbitration clause was a term that was a matter that fell to be determined by the court. Such contention puts the jurisdiction of the arbitrators in issue. The Court relied on *Toller v Law Accident Insurance Society*. This question of *competenz-kompetenz* has also been given effect in the American curial milieu in

AT & T Technology Inc v Communication Workers of America in which it was held as follows: The question of arbitrability whether an agreement creates a duty for the parties to arbitrate a particular grievance is undeniably an issue for judicial and unless the parties clearly otherwise, the question of whether the parties agreed to arbitrate is to be decided by the court not the arbitrator. Similarly in *John Wiley & Sons Inc. v Livingston*, the court reached a similar decision to wit: Under our decision, whether or not the company was bound to arbitrate is a matter to be determined by the court on the basis of the contract entered into by the parties. The duty to arbitrate being of contractual origin, a compulsory submitting to arbitration cannot precede judicial determination that the agreement does in fact create such a duty.

(v) Interim Measures of Protection

An arbitral dispute which involves a res that may be in danger of waste or which is in the hand of a third party who may deal with the same without the consent of the parties needs to be protected in the interim. Where the res is in the possession of one of the parties not much problem is encountered as save for agreement of the parties, the arbitral tribunal is empowered to make orders for interim preservation of the res in an interim award. Such order take various forms. It may require a party to deposit the res with a third party or to sell the res if it is in a perishable or wasting state. It can be a stop work order. The arbitral panel may equally require a party to provide appropriate security in connection with any measure contained in its protective interim award. On the other hand, where the interim award would affect a third party, the situation is different. With few exceptions, the general law in Anglophone circles is that non-party to a contract cannot bear any burden or benefit directly from the contract. An arbitral arrangement is a contract and as such the arbitral tribunal, not possessing any sovereign force, has no power to compel a non-party to the arbitration to act or refrain from acting in a particular manner in respect of an arbitral rest. In such a situation there is an obvious need to enlist the help of the state to achieve arbitral goal. Would it be wrong for a party in the circumstances to have recourse to the court for assistance such as by applying for an interim order to achieve the goal? Article 26 (3) answers: A request for interim measures addressed by any party to court shall not be deemed incompatible with the agreement to arbitrate, or a waiver of that agreement.

(vi) Enforcement of Arbitral Award

Once the arbitral tribunal renders an award, it becomes *functus officio*, the tribunal thus cannot proceed to enforce its award. The tribunal does not even have the wherewithal to do so. Although an award once rendered becomes binding, and parties are expected to comply with the award without prompting, it is not unusual for the award debtor to ignore the award. Here is the greatest need for a coercive machinery to bring to fruition the whole essence of the arbitral arrangement. At such a time, where else can the aggrieved find succor other than enlisting the aid of the state? Recognizing this need, the Act makes provision for the process of not only

recognizing the existence of the award but also providing the means by which an arbitral award would be enforced. The award creditor can apply to the court for both recognition and enforcement of the award and he may seek the leave of the court or a judge to enforce the award in the same manner as a judgment or order of the court. For this reason also, various High court rules have provisions for the enforcement of arbitral award. The only attack by experts in arbitration in the role of court in enforcement of awards is that the court should undertake the matter with dispatch rather than allowing frivolous opposition to the same. As a matter of general approach, the court should strive to uphold the arbitration awards. They should not approach them with a meticulous legal eye, endeavouring to pick holes, inconsistencies and faults in awards and with the objective of upsetting, and frustrating the process of arbitration. The approach should be to read an arbitration award in a reasonable and commercial way, expecting, as is usually the case, that there will be no substantial fault that can be found with it. The reason given by the arbitrator in an award should be read fairly and as a whole. An award should not be vitiated by fine points. The modern approach is in favour of sustaining awards where that can fairly be done, rather than destroying them. The court should not allow the finality of awards to be destroyed unless there is a compelling reason for that. Secondly, counsel to parties should not be allowed to present unfortunate opposition to awards in order to buy time and frustrate the successful party from reaping the fruits of his awards. The situations in our courts where mere application to enforce awards lasts for eleven to thirteen years are both unfortunate and contrary to the philosophy of arbitration.

(vii) Impeachment of an Award

It may also be the case that the award debtor is not satisfied with the outcome of the arbitral processes. Generally, parties take their arbitrator for good or bad since by opting for private settlement, they thereby imply that they have implicit confidence in the arbitral process and have waived their right to a court trial. However, as in every human venture there are often exceptions and derogations reserved in order to address issues arising out of human imperfection and vagaries. Thus the law makes specific and limited provision for an aggrieved party to have the award either wholly or partially set aside: It must be stressed that this provision is not akin to an appeal. There is no wholesale examination of the processes and proceedings of the arbitration. What is required is for the aggrieved award debtor to apply to the court to set aside the award on any of the following grounds:

- (a) that the award contains decisions on matters which are beyond the scope of the submission to arbitration, so however, that if the decision on matters submitted to arbitration can be separated from those not submitted, only the part of the award which contains decisions on matters not submitted may be set aside.
- (b) That the arbitrator misconducted himself or that the award has been improperly procured.
- (c) That there is error of law.
- (d) That the award was improperly procured. (e) There is also the sort of ancillary provisions enabling a party to pray

The court to refuse recognition and enforcement of an award, even when the Award creditor has commenced action to get the award enforced. Generally, arbitration is characterized by flexibility and freedom from rigid procedures of litigation. Nevertheless, Courts must maintain a residual supervisory

jurisdiction to ensure that the fundamental principles of due process, natural justice and the reasonable expectations of the parties are met and observed. As stated above the courts are granted the jurisdiction to impeach an award where there is a violation of the provisions of SS.29 and 30 of the Act and also where the basic rights of the parties have been breached. The advantages of arbitration are lost where courts seek to intervene outside these specific areas, or for tenuous reasons with those areas. Overly strict evaluation of awards may mean parties are, in effect, forced to comply with rigid court procedures rather than flexible arbitral procedures, contrary to their original agreement. Moreover, since the parties to arbitration agreement have agreed to accept the findings of the arbitral tribunal, courts should not attempt to "second-guess" the arbitral procedural rulings.

(viii) Impeaching the Arbitrator

Although generally the court does not intervene in the arbitral processes, yet circumstances may exist calling for some external intervention for this reason it is the law that a court shall not intervene in any matter governed by the Arbitration and Conciliation Act, except in circumstances where the Act permits such intervention. Instances of such include removal of an arbitrator where he has misconducted himself. Misconduct in this instance has nothing to do with moral laxity on the part of the arbitrator. Although the Act did not provide the meaning of misconduct, Black's Law Dictionary defines misconduct as a dereliction of duty; unlawful or improper behavior. The expression has acquired a technical meaning. In *William v Wallis & Company*, it was held that misconduct means such a mishandling of the arbitration as is likely to lead to a substantial miscarriage of justice. However in *Taylor Woodrow Nig. Ltd v Suddontsche Etna Werk GMBH*³⁷ the Supreme Court held: The word misconduct is not defined in the law nor is it stated therein what would amount to misconduct on the part of an arbitrator to necessitate the setting aside of his award, It will

be necessary therefore to fall back on the common law to determine what constitutes misconduct. This falling back to the common law is apparently the underpinnings of the decisions, of the Supreme Court in *A. Savoia v A. O. Sonub* where the Supreme Court itemized what constitute misconduct on the part of arbitrator thus: (a) Where the arbitrator fails to comply with the terms, express or implied, in the arbitration agreement;

(b) Where, even if the arbitrator complies with the terms of the arbitration agreement, the arbitrator makes an award which on the grounds of public policy ought not to be enforced;

(c) Where the arbitrator has been bribed or corrupted;

(d) Technical misconduct, such as where the arbitrator makes a mistake as to the scope of the authority conferred by the agreement of reference. This, however, does not mean that every irregularity of procedure amounts to misconduct,

(e) Where the arbitrator fails to decide all the matters which were referred to him; (f) Where the arbitrator or umpire has breached the rules of natural justice; by hearing one party but refusing to hear the other, or (ii) by deciding the case on a point not put forward by the parties. This decision has been criticized as importing wholesale the impurities of the common law into modern arbitration which is incompatible with the spirit and *raison d'etre* for the enacting of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act whose purpose is essentially to cure the mischief created by common law.

Ix Revocation of Arbitration Agreement

Section 2 of the Act, which is the Arbitration and Conciliation Act, Cap A18 provides that "unless a contrary intention is expressed therein, an arbitration agreement shall be irrevocable except by agreement of the parties or by leave of the court or a judge". Unfortunately, the section failed to state the grounds and circumstances which may give rise to revocation of arbitration agreement by the court or a judge. It may be right to state that supervening impossibility of performance and supervening illegality of performance could constitute such circumstances. In both cases, the application to revoke the arbitration agreement by the court is based on frustration of the arbitration agreement. It could also arise where the agreement was obtained by fraud and misrepresentation or undue influence. Under the English Law, power to revoke arbitration agreement includes power to revoke the mandate of the arbitral tribunal. This is because under the English Law, arbitration agreement involves two separate relationships, that is, the agreement between the parties to be bound by the arbitral award and the mandate granted to the arbitral tribunal to make a binding award at the end of its proceedings. However, as section 2 of the Act stands now, it may be wrong to read into it the power of the court to revoke the mandate of the arbitrators seeing that the reason for the revocation of the mandate of the arbitrators exists

in sections 9 and 10 of the Act. However, where the arbitration agreement is revoked by the order of the court, the mandate of the arbitrator to arbitrate is deemed extinguished. The mandate of the arbitral tribunal will automatically come to an end immediately the agreement is revoked as the arbitration agreement is the legal basis for every arbitration.

x. Power to Compel the Attendance of Witnesses

In arbitration proceedings, it is ordinarily expected that every party should attend the proceedings with his own witness. However, this is not always the case as situations exist wherein recalcitrant witnesses may refuse to attend. As arbitral tribunal is not a court in the conventional sense and as arbitrators are not judges or judicial officers in the judicial sense, application for compelling attendance of witnesses shall be made to a court of competent jurisdiction having the authority to entertain matters with respect to the subject matter in issue. Section 23 of the Act provides that "the court or a judge may order that a writ of subpoena ad testificandum or of suponena duces tecum shall issue to compel the attendance before any arbitral tribunal of a witness wherever he may be in Nigeria" Where the witness sought to be invited is in any prison in Nigeria, the court or judge may order for his attendance. In that regard, the warrant for his production shall be signed by the judge making the order. As a prisoner is held under public law by the order of a court, an arbitral tribunal cannot on its own invite the prisoner to attend its proceedings. Such a prisoner can only attend the arbitral proceedings on the order of a court of competent jurisdiction. By the provisions of section 23(2) of the Act, "the court or a judge may also order that a writ of habeas corpus ad testificandum shall issue to bring up a prisoner for examination before any arbitral tribunal". As regards the service of the witness summons or order of the court, the law pursuant to section 23(3) is that the provisions of any written law relating to service or execution outside a state of the Federation of any such subpoena or order for the production of a prisoner issued or made in civil proceedings by the High Court shall apply.

xi. The relationship of the Court and Arbitration

Before now, the relationship between the courts and the arbitral process was not a cordial one. The courts being highly jealous of their jurisdiction refused to recognize arbitration agreements and awards at the early stages of arbitration practice. This position was succinctly presented by Lord Campell in *Scott v Avery*. The court in this case held that; I know that there has been a very great inclination in the courts for a good many years to throw obstacles in the way of arbitration. I wish to speak with great respect of my predecessors the judges, but I must just let your Lordships into secret of that tendency. There is no disguising the fact that as formerly the emolument of the judges depended mainly or almost entirely upon fees and they had no fixed salary, there was great competition to get as much as possible of litigation into Westminster Hall, and a great scramble in Westminster Hall for the division of the spoil, and hence the dispute between the different courts about the effect of a *latitat*, *capias*, and a *quo minus*- the *latiat* bringing business into the court of Queen's Bench, the *capias* into the Common Pleas, and the *quo minus* into the Exchequer. They had jealousy of arbitration whereby Westminster Hall was robbed of those cases which came neither into the Queen's Bench, nor Common Pleas nor Exchequer. In the mid sixteenth century, the prejudice, suspicion and jealousy placed on arbitration by the courts had dissipated and eroded. This was favoured by the decision in *Mitsubishi Motor Corporation v. Solar Crystal Plymouth Inc.* where Blackman, J. of the United States Supreme Court observed that "we are well past the time when judicial suspicion of the desirability of arbitration and of the competence of arbitral tribunals inhibited the development of arbitration as an alternative measure of dispute resolution" Even in *Okpurunvu v. Okpokam Oguntade J.C.A.*, in a dissenting judgment declares as follows:- The regular courts in the early stages of arbitration were reluctant to accord recognition to the decisions or awards reasoning that arbitration constitutes a rival body to the court. But it was soon realized that arbitration may in fact prove the best way of settling some types of disputes. The attitude of the regular courts to arbitration therefore gradually changed. It was then realized and acknowledged that if parties to dispute voluntarily submit their dispute to a third party as arbitrator and agreed to be bound by the decision of such arbitration, the court must clothe such decision with the garb of *estoppel per rem judicatam*. The prejudice originally held against arbitration no longer exists as courts and judges have recognized and realized that arbitrators and judges are partners in dispensing justice, the judges being appointed by public law. It is today not strange to see judges recommending arbitration to litigants before the court. Both lawyers and judges now see it that arbitration is not only good but cheaper, more efficient, less rancorous, informal and friendlier. However, it is worthy of note to state that arbitration cannot exist independent of the court. Though the court has to interfere within the limit of what is provided by law so as not to render arbitration hopeless.

Conclusion

State Courts provide essential support and assistance for the arbitral process. The great quest for arbitration is that it seeks the co-operation of the very public authorities from which it wants to free itself. Therefore a harmonious relationship between the courts and arbitration is vital and of central importance. This has always involved a delicate balance, since the urge of any judge is to see justice

done, and to right injustice wherever he or she finds it and if it is found in arbitration, why then the judge feels the need to intervene. On the other hand, those active in the world of arbitration stress its voluntary nature, and urge that it is wrong in principle for the courts to concern themselves with disputes which the parties have formally chosen to withdraw from them, quite apart from the waste of time and expense caused by the problem is the extent of weight to give to each of them. Where Blackman, J. of the United States Supreme Court observed that "we are well past the time when judicial suspicion of the desirability of arbitration and of the competence of arbitral tribunals inhibited the development of arbitration as an alternative measure of dispute resolution." Even in *Okpuruwu v. Okpokam*. Arbitration will be a meaningless exercise if the courts are by legislation barred from interfering with arbitration completely. This is because arbitration has no internal mechanism for undertaking certain acts particularly where a party or parties have failed to act with good faith or where a party has failed to undertake the task imposed on him or them by law. It is for this reason that a balance is to be maintained by a recognition by the courts that just as arbitration exists only to serve the interests of the community, so also their own powers are conferred only to support, not supplant, the extra judicial process which the parties have chosen to adopt. Precisely, the same consideration applies to procedure in the arbitration. The parties have chosen to arbitrate, not litigate. By doing so they have selected the procedure laid down in the Arbitration and Conciliation Act or the Arbitration Convention applicable to them. Where they failed to specify the governing procedure, the arbitrators shall have the right and the task of specifying the applicable procedure. This is another choice which the court must respect. The court may feel that the procedure adopted by the arbitrator is unsuitable or may occasion delay, the fact remains that the law has given the arbitrator the right to so act and the courts must not interfere. The courts are to interfere within the limit of what the law has granted to it as set out in section 36 of the Act. Finally, the extent of intervention by the Courts must be fair and just. The Courts must not look at arbitration as if it is court by another name particularly as arbitration is not bound by the strict rules of the Evidence Act and our Civil Procedure Rules.

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